

Co-funded by
the European UnionThe official **newsletter** of the Green Hive Project**July 2024**

content

- ABOUT GREEN HIVE **P.2**
- PROJECT RESULTS **P.3**
- TOOLKIT FOR GREEN
COMBS **P.4**

The project

Green Hive is a Cooperation Partnership in Vocational Education and Training (VET), co-funded by the **Erasmus+ Programme of the EU**. The project, implemented by the Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (Ireland), Lascò (Italy), KEAN (Greece), Femxa (Spain) and Team 4 Excellence (Romania), aims to develop a **European platform-based Ecosystem for Sustainability Education**.

GREEN HIVE OVERVIEW

THE PROJECT

Green Hive is establishing a European network to innovate sustainability education through collaboration among institutes, students, and communities. This initiative involves a diverse range of external stakeholders, including users, the academic world, and the social and private sectors, all actively participating in Green Hive activities. The network is coordinated by a consortium of project partners from Ireland, Italy, Greece, Spain, and Romania, who provide capacity development opportunities, hackathons, and contests to enhance the learning experience within the hubs.

THE HIVE

Central to Green Hive are the Green Combs, localized hubs within vocational training entities (VET providers). These hubs serve as the focal point for disseminating information, insights, and inspiration on sustainability challenges. They aim to connect people and build local communities around sustainability through various events, learning opportunities, and collaborative workshops. By fostering an environment of innovation and co-creation, the Green Combs help students and external stakeholders design and implement sustainable solutions, thereby contributing to a broader, long-term cooperation network dedicated to continuous improvement in sustainability education.

40

Towards permanent **co-creation structures in VET institutions** to enable students to think in systems, understand the interconnectedness of the economy, society and environment, and ultimately develop their systemic and critical thinking competencies by collaborating with other students and external stakeholders

PROJECT RESULTS

Four main results will be co-developed with over 500 VET experts in the scope of the project.

➤➤➤ METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

A **Methodological Framework** for developing a VET sustainability education ecosystem and localised hubs to facilitate the transfer of local experience, knowledge and innovation in the field of the implementation of the **European Sustainability Competence Framework "GreenComp"**, and encourage collective actions of VET providers, learners and external stakeholders to co-create solutions for sustainability

➤➤➤ TOOLKIT FOR GREEN COMBS

A "**Toolkit for the setup and management of Green Combs**", including a how-to guide and canvases to support VET providers in setting up, managing and growing internal hubs for sustainability education;

➤➤➤ EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

Educational resources for Green Combs, including guidelines to implement open spaces for discussion around learner-generated topics among members of localised hubs, micro-learning videos, workshop scenarios and project-based learning experiences in the four competence areas of the GreenComp;

➤➤➤ THE GREEN HIVE PLATFORM

The "Green Hive" platform will **connect the hubs through the Internet and provide capacity-building opportunities and digital tools** for VET institutions, knowledge-transfer spaces, and co-creation activities for its members. By the end of 2025, the Green Hive is expected to host and connect at least 15 localised hubs and 200 VET learners in 5 countries.

TOOLKIT FOR GREEN COMBS

During the last months the consortium worked continuously to create a toolkit for VET institutions to set up and manage internal sustainability education hubs. The toolkit is composed of the following tools:

1. A **How-to Guide** (ePublication) for VET providers, detailing the **processes, tools** and **methods to set up a Green Comb** in six development domains (Governance, Organization, Community, Activities, Tools, Relationships with the Hive). In order to create this publication 3 Multi-Stakeholder Working Groups were held in each partner country and a final international Co-creation lab. The experts provided outlines and valuable knowledge that contributed. You can find the publication [here](#).

TOOLKIT FOR GREEN COMBS

2. A set of min. **12 Canvases**, addressed to Combs' coordinators, to facilitate the management and growth of the hubs in each developmental domain. You can find the canvases [here](#).

3. A **9-module MOOC** addressed to Combs' coordinators, explaining: The EU sustainability competence Framework; best practices and opportunities in Implementing the GreenComp; system innovation approach to fostering sustainability competences in VET; the six domains to manage and nurture Green Combs. The consortium is currently piloting the MOOC with VET teachers, directors, and administrative staff of VET institutions, who are engaged as early adopters of the project's methodology and tools.

The tool kit can be adopted by other VET, School, Higher and Adult Education providers or nonprofit organisations, to develop internal hubs for developing sustainability competences, and/or used to develop communities and activities addressing sustainability challenges. The activities will also contribute to increasing the knowledge and skills of VET teachers and trainers from the countries involved in sustainability education.

VIRTUAL KNOWLEDGE FAIR

The Green Hive project consortium is organizing a **Virtual Knowledge Fair** on **September 2nd and 3rd**, 2024, targeting teachers and trainers from Greece, Italy, Ireland, Romania, and Spain who are keen to **exchange experiences, practices, and ideas** on sustainability education and green skills development with colleagues from across the EU. This online event will feature a fully immersive 3D environment accessible throughout both days, allowing participants to explore sustainability education practices at their leisure. Additionally, there will be two synchronous workshops in English each day, where experts from the Green Hive consortium will facilitate discussions on sustainability competence development. The outcomes of the Fair will contribute to creating a collection of free, reusable educational resources on sustainability for educators.

Wish to learn more about the VKF? <https://www.greenhiveproject.eu/el/news/virtual-knowledge-fair>

Would you like to learn more? Reach out to us anytime via the project website [greenhiveproject.eu](https://www.greenhiveproject.eu) if you have any questions or would like more information.